

Metric Space: How the Notion of “Distance” is Made Abstract in Mathematics

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It is easy to say about “distance” in real world. We can say that the distance between two separate objects can be given by the length of the straight line connecting these objects. Another way, we can say the distance between city A and city B is the length of the shortest route that we travel from city A to city B and vice versa. But when it comes to “distance” between two non-spatial objects, let’s say the distance between two words, or between two DNA sequences, or between the predicted result of a machine learning model and the actual validation dataset, the case might be a little tricky at first glance. In fact, mathematics borrows the notion of distance from the real world and makes it a beautiful abstract notion applicable to a wider range of problems such as mathematical analysis, programming, machine learning, and even biology as we shall see how.

There are no advanced prerequisites for this article. Perhaps, only understanding basic concepts of sets, functions, logic and basic arithmetic are those required, which we cover in Appendix (Section A).

Abstract Properties of Real World Distance

Let us now observe closely what properties we can extract from the notion of “distance” we usually encounter in the real world.

Suppose two point particles a and b separated by some distance ℓ as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Two points in space

Let us now draw the following observations:

1. The first observation to be made is that the distance of any two points must be a nonnegative number, and hence $\ell \geq 0$. Note that we cannot have a negative distance between two points. We may formally write: $d(a, b) \geq 0$
2. The second observation is that the distance of two particles is zero if and only if the two particles are identical (precisely the same particle). This observation is very clear in the real world setting as you see that the distance of an object with itself is zero. Hence, we may formally write: $d(a, b) = 0 \iff a = b$.¹
3. The third observation is that the distance from particle a to b is just the same with the distance from particle b to a . And we may formally write: $d(a, b) = d(b, a)$

¹See Appendix A.2 for the explanation about the logical connective “ \iff ”.

4. The fourth observation is that given an additional particle c to the existing a and b , the distance from a to b is less than or equal to the distance from a to c added with the distance from c to b . Take your time to think about it. For an easier intuitive understanding, observe Figure 2 to support this argument. By combining scenario 1 and scenario 2 from the illustration in Figure 2, we conclude: $d(a, b) \leq d(a, c) + d(c, b)$

Figure 2: Triangle inequality

Take your time to really digest our 4 observations above, since they are crucial in the abstraction of “distance” in mathematics.

Our 4 observations above capture the abstract properties of the notion “distance” in mathematics.

Metric Space

In pure mathematics, instead of sticking to the rigid notion of distance as the length of straight line connecting 2 points, mathematicians devised a concept called “metric” along with the space in which it is well-defined as [metric space](#) [7]. A metric must satisfy all our 4 observations above. We will see later why this designation is very

brilliant and useful. First, let us present the formal definition of metric space as follows.

Definition 1 (Metric Space). Let X be a set². Suppose a map³ $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ ⁴. The map d is called a metric [7] if and only if the following axioms hold:

M1 $d(a, b) \geq 0$, for every $a, b \in X$.

M2 $d(a, b) = 0 \iff a = b$, for every $a, b \in X$.

M3 $d(a, b) = d(b, a)$, for every $a, b \in X$.

M4 $d(a, b) \leq d(a, c) + d(c, b)$, for every $a, b, c \in X$.

If d is a metric on X , then the pair (X, d) is called a metric space [7].

Note that axioms M1, M2, M3 and M4 are precisely the abstraction and formalism of our 4 observations earlier. Axiom M1 is known as the **nonnegativity** of metric space, axiom M2 is known as the **point separating axiom**, axiom M3 is known as the **symmetric axiom** and axiom M4 is known as the **triangle inequality**.

Other Concrete Forms of Distance Under the Same Notion of Metric

We now shall see why “metric” matters. The underlying concept of distance that we have presented earlier is commonly referred to as the **Euclidean metric space**, in which the distance between two points are defined as the length of the straight line separating them. Now, we shall see another different form of distance but still a metric on the same underlying set.

Taxicab Metric

Now suppose a flat two dimensional space and two points a and b on the space similar to the 1 earlier. This time, instead of defining the distance of a and b as the length of the straight line separating these points, we define it as the total length of the shortest vertical and horizontal lines in the grid connecting this two points. You can think of this mechanism as a rule in which beings living on this space can only move on the grid lines. Observe the illustration in Figure 3.

²See Appendix A.1 for the explanation of set.

³See Appendix A.3 for the explanation of map.

⁴The readers are referred to Definition 11 for the explanation of the expression $X \times X$.

Figure 3: Taxicab metric

Now let us evaluate whether this scenario make the space and the distance system a metric space:

1. Obviously, the values of ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 are nonnegative, and hence, $\ell_1 + \ell_2 \geq 0$. This result satisfies the nonnegativity axiom (axiom M1).
2. This system also satisfies the point separating axiom (axiom M2) since you can only get $d(a, b) = 0$ if and only if $\ell_1 = \ell_2 = 0$ which means that $a = b$.
3. In this system, the distance from a to b is given by $d(a, b) = \ell_1 + \ell_2$, while the distance from b to a is given by $d(b, a) = \ell_2 + \ell_1$. Since addition of numbers is commutative, that is, $\ell_1 + \ell_2 = \ell_2 + \ell_1$, then we have $d(a, b) = d(b, a)$, which eventually shows that the symmetric axiom (axiom M3) holds.
4. To show the triangle inequality (axiom M4), let us add a point c in the system and observe the illustration in Figure 4. From both scenario 1 and scenario 2 in Figure 4, we obtain $d(a, b) \leq d(a, c) + d(c, b)$, showing that the triangle inequality (axiom M4) holds.

Since all metric space axioms hold, we conclude that this system is a metric space. In fact, there is a fancy name for this metric; the **taxicab⁵metric**, and the space is sometimes referred to as a **taxicab metric space**.

⁵The name “taxicab” was given since the grid system makes it look like a grid-like city street in which taxicabs are passing through, like those in Manhattan [4] This name was given by the mathematician Karl Menger.

Figure 4: Taxicab triangle inequality

Other Examples of Metric Space Similar to the Taxicab Metric Space

Both the taxicab metric space and the Euclidean metric space allow us to define distance between two points in the same space based on their respective rules. Note that the underlying space of the taxicab metric space and the Euclidean metric space is the same, and in our examples, it is a two dimensional plane space. There are other similar metric space as these two with the same underlying space, including the [Minkowski metric space](#), and the [Chebyshev metric space](#).

Interesting Metric Spaces

We will now see how we can define metric spaces on many real world cases, even on non-spatial objects.

Words Metric Space

If you are asked, what is the distance between the word “abstrak” and the word “abstract”? It might first sound a little bit weird. With metric space, we can make

such a question sensible.

Now let W denote the set of all known words in Latin alphabet. So both “abstrak” and “abstract” are elements of W , or we can formally write

$$\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract} \in W.$$

Now suppose a map $d : W \times W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$d(v, w) := (\text{the maximum number of placeholders with different letters}),$$

for any two words $v, w \in W$. Let us now present an example for clarity. The distance between “abstrak” and “abstract” is 2, as given by

$$d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract}) = 2,$$

since there are maximally two placeholders in both words with different letters:

abstrak abstract

Let us now observe that this system, (W, d) , is in fact a metric space.

1. We assume that there are only finitely many letters in all words in all human languages. So, the number of placeholders with different letters for any two words must always be finite. And such a number is nonnegative. Hence, the nonnegativity axiom (axiom **M1**) is satisfied.
2. Two words are different as long as they have placeholders with different letters. Otherwise, they are identical words. It implies that $d(v, w) = 0 \iff v = w$, for any two words $v, w \in W$. Hence, the point separating axiom (axiom **M2**) is also satisfied.
3. Let us take a closer look at the distance of “abstrak” and “abstract”. Note that

$$d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract}) = 2 = d(\text{abstract}, \text{abstrak})$$

holds. And it applies to any pair of words. Hence, the symmetric axiom (axiom **M3**) is also satisfied.

4. Now consider another word “algebra”. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract}) &= 2 \\ &< 6 + 7 \\ &= d(\text{abstrak}, \text{algebra}) + d(\text{abstract}, \text{algebra}) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract}) &= 2 \\
 &= 0 + 2 \\
 &= d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstrak}) + d(\text{abstrak}, \text{abstract}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that this mechanism also applies to any pair of words. And thus, we conclude $d(v, w) \leq d(v, x) + d(x, w)$, for any words $v, w, x \in W$. Hence, the triangle inequality (axiom M4) is also satisfied.

From our observations above, we conclude that (W, d) is a metric space. Let us call (W, d) the words metric space.

DNA Metric Space

Now let us explore a more interesting example. DNA, which stands for “Deoxyribonucleic acid”, is a polymer composed of two polynucleotide chains that coil around each other to form a double helix [9]. The information about DNA is codified into a DNA sequence. A DNA sequence can provide information of human genome.

Two examples of DNA sequence are given by ACGT and AGGT. Each letters in these sequences represent nucleotide bases [10]; A represents Adenine, C represents Cytosine, G represents Guanin and T represents Thymine. Now let \mathcal{D} be the set of all DNA sequences. So, we may express $ACGT, AGGT \in \mathcal{D}$. You might guess what next? Yes, we can also define a distance between a pair of DNA sequences precisely like the words metric space as a map $d : \mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by considering the distance two DNA sequences is the maximum number of placeholders in both sequences with different nucleotide bases. So, the distance between ACGT and AGGT is given by

$$d(\text{ACGT}, \text{AGGT}) = 1.$$

We will not provide a thorough observation to confirm that (\mathcal{D}, d) is indeed a metric space, since we think it is obvious. Interested readers can try to do their own observations, which can be done similar to the words metric space earlier. We can call (\mathcal{D}, d) the DNA metric space.

Hamming Distance

We can see that the rule for the metric d in both the words metric space (W, d) and the DNA metric space (\mathcal{D}, d) is the same. In fact, there is a metric space generalising both (W, d) and (\mathcal{D}, d) called Hamming metric space. And the metric d

in a Hamming metric space is called Hamming distance (or Hamming metric). Let us present the formal definition of Hamming metric space as follows.

Definition 2 (Hamming Metric Space). Let X be the set of strings of characters. For instance the string abc is in X , i.e., $abc \in X$. A metric $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$d(s, t) := (\text{the maximum number of placeholders with different characters})$$

for every strings $s, t \in X$, is called a Hamming distance (or Hamming metric) [3]. And we call (X, d) a Hamming metric space.

It is evident from Definition 2 that both the words metric space (W, d) and the DNA metric space (\mathcal{D}, d) are Hamming metric spaces. Another well-known application of Hamming metric space is in the error correction code in information theory [3].

Metric Space of Mean Absolute Error

For those of you who are familiar with machine learning (ML) or statistics must also be familiar with **Mean Absolute Error** (MAE). In ML, MAE is a numeric indicator which quantitatively tells how good is our ML model with respect to the dataset, especially for regression models.

We will now get our hands a little dirty to show that in fact MAE defines a metric on the space of weight vectors [5] for a multilinear regression ML model.

The rest of the discussion in this subsection requires a sufficient mathematical knowledge and familiarity with machine learning or statistics. Interested readers may continue. Otherwise, you can skip the rest of this section.

Now suppose a natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Suppose we have an n -linear regression ML model given by a map $\text{ML} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which takes the form

$$\text{ML}(x_1, \dots, x_n) := \sum_{k=0}^n w_k x_k$$

for every $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}$ and for some weights $w_0, w_1, \dots, w_n \in \mathbb{R}$ where $x_0 := 1$. The training of the ML is to determine the weight vector $\mathbf{w} := (w_0, w_1, \dots, w_n)$.

How good our ML model on predicting the unseen data can be determined by evaluating the MAE of the prediction on the validation dataset. Suppose our validation dataset has N data points, for some natural number $N \in \mathbb{N}$ with $N > 3$. Let the N -dimensional vector $\mathbf{y} := (y_1, \dots, y_N)$ be the values of the output in the

validation dataset. And suppose the ML predicted values on the validation input is the vector $\hat{\mathbf{y}} := (\hat{y}_1, \dots, \hat{y}_N)$. The MAE of our ML model with respect to the validation dataset is given by

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) := \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |y_k - \hat{y}_k|. \quad (1)$$

We claim that MAE can be represented by a map $\text{MAE} : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which is a metric on \mathbb{R}^N . This claim is confirmed through the following observations:

1. Look at the summation expression on the definition of MAE in Equation 1, that is, the expression

$$\sum_{k=1}^N |y_k - \hat{y}_k|.$$

This expression is in fact the taxicab metric on \mathbb{R}^N . The underlying space of our earlier example on taxicab metric is the plane spatial space, which is denoted by \mathbb{R}^2 . And it is easy to visualise \mathbb{R}^2 as we have presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Sadly, we cannot visualise \mathbb{R}^N when $N > 3$. If we think \mathbb{R}^2 as a planar grid universe, we can think of \mathbb{R}^N as N -dimensional grid universe. Note that $|y_k - \hat{y}_k|$ is the length of the k -th grid component connecting the points \mathbf{y} and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, for every $k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. To make the analogy with \mathbb{R}^2 earlier even better, we may denote $\ell_k := |y_k - \hat{y}_k|$. Similar to the observations for the earlier taxicab metric, this taxicab metric is confirmed to be a metric on \mathbb{R}^N .

2. Since, we have confirmed that the summation is a taxicab metric, let us denote it by a map $d_1 : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Hence, MAE can be rewritten into a map $\text{MAE} : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) := \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})}{N} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |a_k - b_k|$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

3. Note that since d_1 is a taxicab metric, it satisfies all metric space axioms. The division by the number N on d_1 makes MAE remains nonnegative, that is,

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})}{N} \geq 0$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. It shows that MAE satisfies the nonnegativity axiom (axiom M1).

4. Since d_1 is a metric, d_1 satisfies the point separating axiom (axiom M2), and we have

$$d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0 \iff \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Division by N does not change this property, and hence, we obtain

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})}{N} = 0 \iff \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, which shows that the point separating axiom (axiom M2) is also satisfied.

5. Since d_1 is a metric, d_1 satisfies the symmetric axiom (axiom M3), and we have

$$d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = d_1(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Division by N does not change this property, and hence, we obtain

$$\text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})}{N} = \frac{d_1(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})}{N} = \text{MAE}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, which shows that the symmetric axiom (axiom M3) is also satisfied.

6. Since d_1 is a metric, d_1 satisfies the triangle inequality (axiom M4), and we have

$$d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \leq d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) + d_1(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Again, division by N does not change this property, and hence we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})}{N} \\ &\leq \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) + d_1(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})}{N} \\ &= \frac{d_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})}{N} + \frac{d_1(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})}{N} \\ &= \text{MAE}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) + \text{MAE}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) \end{aligned}$$

for every $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, showing that the triangle inequality (axiom M4) is also satisfied.

With all the observations above, we confirm that MAE is a metric on \mathbb{R}^N . In other words, $(\mathbb{R}^N, \text{MAE})$ is a metric space.

In a ML model, the less the value of MAE on both the training and validation datasets, the better the model performs. In the framework of metric space, we can also say that our ML model gives a good performance as the distance between the prediction and the validation is close enough.

Final Thought

It is fascinating to observe how the seemingly concrete notion of distance in the real world can be abstracted through the lens of pure mathematics using the concept of a metric space. A metric space generalises the idea of distance, allowing us to rigorously define and analyse “distances” in contexts far removed from the physical world. This abstraction not only enriches mathematical theory but also has profound and widespread applications across diverse fields, like linguistics, biology, information theory and machine learning as we have seen in this article.

Such examples illustrate the transformative power of pure mathematics. By distilling concepts to their essence, mathematics provides tools and frameworks that transcend specific problems or domains, enabling solutions to emerge in unexpected contexts. This is why engaging with abstract mathematics can be far more compelling and intellectually stimulating than focusing solely on concrete applications. It challenges us to think deeply, fosters creativity, and reveals the interconnectedness of seemingly unrelated phenomena. Pure mathematics isn't just about solving problems—it's about expanding the horizon of what can be understood and achieved.

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A Appendix

A.1 Set

Definition 3 (Set). A set is any collection of things [8].

Usually, a set is denoted by a capital letter or a special letters like those of sets of numbers. In fact, there are no specific rules. The most important is that the author states that a certain letter defines a set.

A collection $V := \{a, e, i, o, u\}$ of vowel letters in alphabet can be considered as a set. A set is also commonly written as a list of the set elements within curly braces “{}”.

Important sets in mathematics are sets of numbers which are presented in the following definitions.

Definition 4 (Set \mathbb{N}). The notation \mathbb{N} denotes the set of all natural numbers [8]. Natural numbers are the numbers $0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$ and so on.

Definition 5 (Set \mathbb{Z}). The notation \mathbb{Z} denotes the set of all integers [8]. Integers are numbers $\dots, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$ and so on. Therefore, all natural numbers are integers.

Definition 6 (Set \mathbb{Q}). The notation \mathbb{Q} denotes the set of all rational numbers [8]. A rational number is the number which can be express as the division of an integer with a nonzero integer. For instance, the number $-\frac{1}{2}$ is a rational number, since we can express this number as the division of -1 with 2 . Note that all integers are rational numbers as we can express an integer n as $n = \frac{n}{1}$.

Definition 7 (Set \mathbb{R}). The notation \mathbb{R} denotes the set of all real numbers [8]. A real number is any number in the number line in between $-\infty$ and ∞ [6]. Note that $-\infty$ and ∞ are not real numbers. All natural numbers are real numbers, all integers are real numbers and all rational numbers are real numbers. The real numbers that are not rational numbers are called irrational numbers. Two examples of irrational numbers are the Euler number e [6] and π .

Definition 8 (Set \mathbb{C}). The notation \mathbb{C} denotes the set of all complex numbers [8]. A complex number z is a number of the form

$$z = a + bi$$

where a and b are real numbers and $i := \sqrt{-1}$. Note that $\sqrt{-1}$ is not a real number, since it does not have a place on the number line. Therefore, all real numbers are complex number since we can express a real number x as $x = x + 0 \cdot i$.

While \mathbb{R} will, perhaps, be the only set of numbers which occurs in our discussion on metric space, we think it is worth explaining the basic number sets in mathematics.

Definition 9 (Set Membership). Suppose X is a set. The matter (or thing) in a set is referred to as “member” or “element”. If x is an element of the set X , we symbolically state $x \in X$. The notation “ \in ” is called the set-membership notation. If y is not an element of X , we symbolically state $y \notin X$.

For instance, we can state $1, 2, 3 \in \mathbb{N}$, $-23, 14 \in \mathbb{Z}$, $-\frac{e}{\pi} \in \mathbb{R}$ and $3 + \pi i \in \mathbb{C}$. And for the set of vowels V , we can state $a \in V$. Likewise, we can state $b \notin V$, $-7 \notin \mathbb{N}$, $\pi \notin \mathbb{Q}$ and $\pi i \notin \mathbb{R}$.

Definition 10 (Subset). Suppose A and B are sets. If all elements of A are also elements of B , then we say that A is a subset of B and we symbolically state $A \subseteq B$. In addition, if there is at least one element of B which is not in A , we say that A is a proper subset of B and we state $A \subset B$.

Hence, we have $\mathbb{N} \subset \mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{R} \subset \mathbb{C}$. And for the vowels set, we have $\{a, i, u\} \subset \{a, e, i, o, u\}$.

Definition 11 (Cartesian Product). Let X and Y be sets. The Cartesian product of X and Y is a set denoted by $X \times Y$ such that every element of $X \times Y$ takes a form (x, y) where $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$.

For an example of Cartesian product, suppose sets

$$A := \{a, b, c\}, \text{ and } X := \{x, y\}.$$

The Cartesian product of A and X is given by

$$A \times X = \{(a, x), (a, y), (b, x), (b, y), (c, x), (c, y)\}.$$

We usually denote the Cartesian product of a set with itself using the exponent notation, for instance, \mathbb{R}^2 for $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$. And the n times Cartesian product of \mathbb{R} is denoted by \mathbb{R}^n , for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

A.2 Logic

The only logical connective [1] which occurs in this article is the biconditional connective “ \iff ”. If P and Q are some logical statements, then $P \iff Q$ is another logical statements with the following truth values:

P	Q	$P \iff Q$
True	True	True
False	True	False
True	False	False
False	False	True

A.3 Map and Function

A map is a relation between two sets [2]. Suppose X and Y are sets. A map f from X to Y is denoted by

$$f : X \rightarrow Y .$$

In this scenario, we can think of X as the input of f while Y is the output of f . Commonly, the set X is called the domain of f while the set Y is called the codomain of f [2]. The requirement for f to be a valid map is that every element $x \in X$ must have a value $f(x) \in Y$ under f .

For a simple example, suppose the set of vowels $V := \{a, e, i, o, u\}$ and define a map $f : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ by the rule

$$f(a) = 1, f(e) = 2, f(i) = 3, f(o) = 4 \text{ and } f(u) = 5 .$$

We say that $f : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a valid map since every element in V has a value in \mathbb{N} .

A map can also be called a function. Other authors, may directly call a map a function. But, we favoured the notion of function to be a map whose output is the set \mathbb{R} . An example of a function is a map $\exp : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\exp(x) := e^x ,$$

for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Another example is a polynomial function $p : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$p(x) := 5 - 4x + 3x^2 - 2x^3 + x^4 ,$$

for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

We can also use Cartesian product of sets as the domain of a map or a function. For example, a multivariate function $g : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$g(x, y) := (x + y)^2 - 2xy$$

for every $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$. In our main discussion, a metric is expressed as a map whose domain is a Cartesian product.

References

- [1] M. Bergmann, J. Moor, and J. Nelson. *The Logic Book (Sixth Edition)*. McGraw-Hill, New York, 2014.
- [2] P. R. Halmos. *Naive Set Theory*. Norstrand, Princeton, 1968.
- [3] E. Kreyszig. *Introductory Functional Analysis with Applications*. Wiley, New York, 1978.
- [4] K. Menger. *You Will Like Geometry: A Guide Book for the Illinois Institute of Technology Geometry Exhibition*. Museum of Science and Industry, 1952.
- [5] S. Roman. *Advanced Linear Algebra (Second Edition)*. Springer, New York, 2005.
- [6] W. Rudin. *Principles of Mathematical Analysis*. McGraw-Hill, New York, 1964.
- [7] M. O. Searcoid. *Metric Spaces*. Springer Verlag, London, 2007.
- [8] R. R. Stoll. *Set Theory and Logic*. Dover, New York, 1963.
- [9] Wikipedia. Dna. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DNA>, 2024. Accessed: 17 November 2024.
- [10] Wikipedia. Nucleotide base. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nucleotide_base, 2024. Accessed: 17 November 2024.